

1 Correction for ECC-CHARMM36 parameter used in J. Phys. Chem. B 2018, 122, 45464557

In "Melcr et al. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 2018, 122, 45464557" we introduced preliminary ECC-CHARMM36 parameters to show that the scaling of partial charges improves cation binding affinity also in CHARMM36 model. According to the text in the section "S3 Electronic continuum correction applied to CHARMM36 model", we scaled the parameters as for Lipid14, i.e., 0.8 for charges and 0.89 for LJ sigma of all atoms in headgroup and glycerol backbone regions. After publication of the work, we realized that the parameters for some atoms were accidentally not scaled, see figure 1 and table 1 for details. Nevertheless, the results reported in the manuscript were not affected, see figures 3 and 7.

Figure 1: Published ECC-CHARMM36 model. The atoms with missing scaling in partial charges (**left**) and LJ sigma (**right**) are shown in red.

Charges of all of the marked atoms were scaled by 0.8. WdV sigmas were scaled by 0.89. Oxygen O32 was left with its original charge by mistake.

Atom	Charge			Sigma		
	Original	Published ECC	Errata	Original	Published ECC	Errata
N	-0.600	-0.480	-0.480	3.29632525712	2.93372947884	2.93372947884
C12	-0.100	-0.080	-0.080	3.58141284692	3.18745743376	3.18745743376
H12A	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
H12B	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
C13	-0.350	-0.280	-0.280	3.67050271874	3.26674741968	3.26674741968
H13A	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
H13B	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
H13C	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
C14	-0.350	-0.280	-0.280	3.67050271874	3.26674741968	3.26674741968
H14A	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
H14B	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
H14C	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
C15	-0.350	-0.280	-0.280	3.67050271874	3.26674741968	3.26674741968
H15A	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
H15B	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
H15C	0.250	0.200	0.200	1.24725820540	1.11005980281	1.11005980281
C11	-0.080	-0.064	-0.064	3.58141284692	3.18745743376	3.18745743376
H11A	0.090	0.072	0.072	2.38760856462	2.12497162251	2.12497162251
H11B	0.090	0.072	0.072	2.38760856462	2.12497162251	2.12497162251
P	1.500	1.342	1.216	3.83086448800	3.40946939432	3.40946939432
O13	-0.780	-0.624	-0.624	3.02905564168	2.69585952110	2.69585952110
O14	-0.780	-0.624	-0.624	3.02905564168	2.69585952110	2.69585952110
O12	-0.570	-0.456	-0.456	2.93996576986	2.93996576986	2.61656953517
O11	-0.570	-0.456	-0.456	2.93996576986	2.93996576986	2.61656953517
C1	-0.080	-0.064	-0.064	3.58141284692	3.58141284692	3.18745743376
HA	0.090	0.072	0.072	2.38760856462	2.38760856462	2.12497162251
HB	0.090	0.072	0.072	2.38760856462	2.38760856462	2.12497162251
C2	0.170	0.136	0.136	4.05358916754	4.05358916754	3.60769435911
HS	0.090	0.072	0.072	2.35197261589	2.35197261589	2.09325562814
O21	-0.490	-0.392	-0.392	2.93996576986	2.93996576986	2.61656953517
C21	0.900	0.720	0.720	3.56359487256	3.56359487256	3.17159943658
O22	-0.630	-0.504	-0.504	3.02905564168	3.02905564168	2.69585952110
C3	0.080	0.064	0.064	3.58141284692	3.58141284692	3.18745743376
HX	0.090	0.072	0.072	2.38760856462	2.38760856462	2.12497162251
HY	0.090	0.072	0.072	2.38760856462	2.38760856462	2.12497162251
O31	-0.490	-0.392	-0.392	2.93996576986	2.93996576986	2.61656953517
C31	0.900	0.720	0.720	3.56359487256	3.56359487256	3.17159943658
O32	-0.630	-0.630	-0.504	3.02905564168	3.02905564168	2.69585952110

Figure 2: Changes of the headgroup order parameters as a function of NaCl (left) and CaCl₂ (right) from simulations with CHARMM36, simulations with ECC-CHARMM36 parameters used in the publication, simulations with corrected ECC-CHARMM36 parameters and experiments.

Density profiles do not change with corrected force-field.

Figure 3: Calcium (**left**) and sodium (**right**) density profiles with the ECC-CHARMM36 parameters used in the publication and with the corrected parameters.

Overall, we can say that the published FF proved the ECC concept.